

INKLYUZIV TA'LIMNI TASHKIL ETISHDA ALOHIDA TA'LIM EHTIYOJLARI MAVJUD BOLALARNING IMKONIYATLARI

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Hozirgi kunda ko'pchilik tomonidan eng bahsli deb tan olingan masala alohida yordamga muhtoj va imkoniyati cheklangan bolalar uchun inklyuziv ta'limni joriy etish masalasidir. Inklyuziv ta'limni joriy etish deganda, imkoniyati cheklangan bolalar uchun xalqaro darajadagi ta'lim sohasining siyosati va tajribasida muhim oqibatlarni nazarda tutiladi.

Inklyuziv ta'lim, inson huquqlarini farqlari va turlarini namoyon qilish, baholash va hisobga olishni, ijtimoiy adolat va adolatlilik masalalarini, shuningdek nogironlikning ijtimoiy modeli va ta'limning ijtimoiy-siyosiy modelini o'z ichiga olgan ko'p tomonlama konsepsiyadan iborat. Shuningdek, maktabni transformatsiya qilish jarayoni va bolalar diqqatini ta'lim olish huquqi va ta'lim olish imkoniyatiga jalb etishni o'z ichiga oladi. Inklyuziv ta'limning umumiy maqsadi sifatida inklyuziv ta'limni talabalarga jamiyat hayotida ishtirok etish imkoniyatini berish vositasi sifatida deb ta'kidlanadi.

Alohida yordamga muhtoj va imkoniyati cheklangan bolalar uchun inklyuziv inklyuziv ta'limi 4 asosiy tamoyilga tayanadi. Bu:

- birinchidan, ko'plab o'quvchilarni umumiy ta'limning ko'plab va'dalar beruvchi, qiziqarli va egiluvchan o'quv dasturlari bilan ta'minlash;

- ikkinchidan, o'ziga jalb etuvchi turfa xillik, kuchli tomonlari va chaqiriqlarga e'tibor berilishi;

- uchinchidan, differensial ta'lim va amaliyotni o'zida aks ettirish yordamida;

- to'rtinchidan, talabalar, o'qituvchilar, oilalar, boshqa mutaxassis va jamoat muassasalari bilan birgalikdagi hamkorlik asosidagi hamjamiyatni tashkil etish.

Maxsus ta'limni keng ko'lamli aniqlashni ta'minlash quyidagicha amalga oshiriladi:

Maxsus ta'lim o'z ichiga xulq-atvor, emotsional, jismoniy, salomatligida yoki sensor rivojlanishida buzilishlari bo'lgan talabalar uchun ularni baholash tajribasi va xizmat ko'rsatish bilan bog'liq bo'lgan maxsus ishlab chiqilgan va koordinatsiyalashtirilgan ilmiy asoslangan uslubiy majmuaviy to'plamini yetkazib berish va monitoring qilishni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu ta'limiy tajribalar va xizmatlar talabalarning alohida kuchli jihatlari va muammoli tomonlarini hisobga olgan holda aniqlanadi va bartaraf etiladi; ularning ta'limiy, ijtimoiy, xatti-harakat (xulq-atvor) va jismoniy rivojlanishlarini oshirish maqsadida; maktab ta'limining, jamoalar va jamiyatning barcha jabhalariga kirish va haqqoniylikni ta'minlash.

Bu shundan darak beradiki, maxsus ta'lim quyidagicha ta'riflanadi:

- Individual baholash va rejalashtirish.
- Ixtisoslashtirilgan ta'lim.
- Intensiv (tezkor) ta'lim.
- Maqsadga yo'naltirilgan ko'rsatma.
- Ta'lim tajribasi asosidagi tadqiqot.
- Hamkorlikdagi sheriklik.
- O'quvchining samaradorlik bahosi.

Maxsus ta’limning rivojlanish davri oxirgi 250 yilni o’z ichiga oladi. Dastlab paydo bo’lgan maktablar bu 1760 yilda karlar uchun va 1780 yillarda ko’r bolalar uchun tashkil etilgan maktablar hisoblanadi. Bulardan keyin 1830 yillarda intellektual imkoniyatlari cheklangan bolalar uchun va 1860 yillarda jismoniy imkoniyatlari cheklangan bolalar uchun maktablar tashkillandi.

1900 yillarda ta’lim olishda qiyinchilikka uchraydigan bolalarga ta’lim beruvchi o’qituvchilar ma’lumot sifatida jahonning turli mamlakatlari bo’yicha barcha bolalarning maktabga borishlarini talab qila boshladilar. shu davrda Binga murojaat qililib, shunday bolalarni aniqlash uchun test yaratishni taklif qilindi. Bu keyinchalik intellektni sinashning 1-usuli bo’lib qoldi. Bu testlardan 20-asr boshlarida ta’limda ma’lum qiyinchiliklari mavjud bo’lgan bolalarning umumta’lim maktablari maxsus sinflarida o’qimishli bo’lishlari uchun tanlab olishda foydalanildi. Ko’pgina mamlakatlarda bunday sinflar soni 1980-yillargacha ortib bordi, shu jumladan AQSH va Yangi Zelandiyada, shundan keyin esa maxsus sinflar soni kamaya boshladi.

So’nggi 30 yil atrofida maxsus ta’lim siyosati va tajribasi yaxlit holatda, shuningdek, qisman umumta’lim maktablaridagi maxsus sinflarning “inklyuziv ta’lim ” deb nomlanishi alternativ holatda shubha ostida qoldi.

Salend Inklyuziv ta’limni aniqlashning foydali jihatlarini quyida tarzda ta’minlaydi:

Bunga falsafani kiritish, qaysiki, talabalarni, ularning oilalarini, o’qituvchilar va hamjamiyat a’zolarini birgalikda o’zaro e’tirof etish va tegishlilik asosidagi maktab tashkil etishga olib keladi. Inklyuzivlashtirilgan maktablarda o’quvchilarning barcha fazilatlarini olqishlash, e’tirof etish, tasdiqlash va namoyish qilish orqali ularni hududlaridagi umumta’lim maktablari sinflari davriga mos keluvchi, yuqori sifatli o’quvchilarni tarbiyalash. Bu shundan dalolat beradiki, inklyuziv ta’lim quyidagicha xarakterlanadi:

- Hamjamiyat doirasidagi qabul qilish va tegishlilik falsafasi;
- Talaba, oila, pedagog va hamjamiyatning hamkorlik falsafasi;
- Barcha o’quvchilarning turli tumanligi va qadriligi belgilanadi;
- Yuqori sifatli maktablardagi o’quvchilarning ma’rifatliligini qadrlash;
- O’z tengqurlari bilan birga o’quvchilarning ma’rifatliligini qadrlash;
- Oddiy sinflarda o’qiydigan o’quvchilarning ma’rifatliligini qadrlash;
- Maktablar va mahalliy hamjamiyatdagi o’quvchilarning tarbiyalanishini qadrlash.

Inklyuziv ta’lim nisbatan yaqin davrda tashkil topgan. Uning ilk kurtaklari davri umumta’lim maktablaridagi ta’lim olishda muayyan qiyinchiliklari mavjud bo’lgan bolalar uchun tashkil etilgan maxsus sinflarning samaradorligiga Dunn shubha bilan qaragan 1960 yillarga to’g’ri keladi. Bu hodisa bunday bolalarni “dolzarblashtirish”ga chaqiradi, ya’ni ularni maxsus sinflarga emas, balki oddiy sinflarga kiritib o’qitish, oxir oqibat umumta’lim maktablarida imkoniyati cheklangan bolalarga ta’lim berish masalasini, boshqacha qilib aytganda, “integratsiyalashtirish” masalasi “ta’lim sohasidagi davomiy tashabbus”deb atala boshlandi.

Yuqorida bayon etilganlardan shu narsa ayon bo’ladiki, inklyuziv ta’lim konstruktiv yo’naltirilgan holda imkoniyati cheklangan bolalarga ta’lim berishni yaxshilashni ta’minlashga harakat qilmoqda. Shunga qaramasdan, yuqoridagi qarashlarga qarama qarshi holda, ayrim mualliflar ta’limning inklyuziv natijalari aqlga zid mafkuraning bolalar uchun qurbonligi, deb ta’kidlaydilar.

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